

2. Healthy and diseased plants of IR26. The infected plant is stunted.

3. Chlorotic streaks and mottling on the leaves, the characteristic symptoms of the disease.

growth of the veins; and stimulation of new tillers. Nodal branching and aerial root formation were also observed. The symptoms varied widely among varieties and ages of infected plants. Some infected plants recovered from the disease.

Both persistent and nonpersistent attempts at transmission by *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus* and *Nilaparvata lugens* and by mechanical means and the seed were unsuccessful. The constant association of the rice mealy bug

Heterococcus rehi (*Ripersia oryzae*) with the disease in the field encouraged us to conduct transmission tests with the insect. In all three tests, each involving 100 test seedlings, transmission with the mealy bug was positive. About 30-40% of the seedlings of Jaya and IR26 are infected when each seedling was inoculated by three infective nymphs; none of the check seedlings showed symptoms. Transmission appeared to be nonpersistent. The transmission pattern, virus-vector relationships and structure of the virus

are being investigated in greater detail.

Previously reported virus and mycoplasma diseases of rice are transmitted by leafhoppers, planthoppers, and beetles, and through mechanical inoculation, but not by the rice mealy bug. The symptoms of the new virus disease are distinctly different from those of the reported diseases. We have therefore named the disease *Chlorotic streak* on the basis of its characteristic symptoms. ■

Ecology, epidemiology, and supervised control of rice brown leaf spot

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The ecology, epidemiology, and supervised control of brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Drechslera oryzae* has been studied in Karnataka. The following observations on brown spot epidemiology were made:

1. The glume blotch phase of the disease, which is the most serious, causes large yield losses.
2. The disease is not strictly seedborne in the sense that seedborne inoculum does not cause the usual disease symptoms such as leaf spotting and glume blotching.

3. The seedborne inoculum causes pre-emergence death of the seedlings only.
4. The pathogen is not soil borne; it survives only 4-6 weeks in puddled or semidry soil. It is highly aerobic and subject to biological antagonism in the soil.
5. The perfect state of the fungus was not found in nature, nor were any collateral hosts found although about 50 grass species were examined.
6. The leaf spots do not sporulate. Sporulation occurred, however, when the leaves were treated with warm water, indicating an inhibitory, water-soluble component in the spot. The leaf spots do not supply the inoculum for glume infection.
7. All the straw samples collected

from several straw ricks in farmers' holdings yielded viable *D. oryzae*.

8. Studies using a suction-type volumetric spore trap for 365 days indicated year-round presence of *D. oryzae* spores in the atmosphere.

9. The number of such spores varied seasonally. The lowest number was 500,000/liter of air in February-March and the highest, 17,000,000/liter of air in November.

10. There was diurnal variation in spore numbers. The maximum was from 0300 to 0900 hours and the minimum, from 1500 to 2100 hours.

11. Seed treatment with hot water does not ensure disease control, and spraying the crop at any stage before heading has no practical value.

Ecology, epidemiology, and control of brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Drechlera oryzae* (Breda de Haan), Subram and Jain in Karnataka.

12. Spraying with a suitable fungicide at heading and during the grain-maturation stage gave excellent disease control.
13. Supervised control of disease

- development leads to economy in fungicide use and more effective control of the glume blotch phase.
14. Brestan + Dithane M-45 (1:5 pro-

portion) at the 0.2% level has effectively controlled the disease. The figure shows the ecology and epidemiology of the disease. ■

Sheath blight control with soil fungicides

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A field trial was established to study the efficiency of certain soil and foliar fungicides against sheath blight disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi, in 1977—78 kharif and rabi. The fungicides thiram, PCNB, and IBP17G were applied to the soil before transplanting. A single edifenphos spray was applied at the maximum tillering stage, except in plots treated with IBP17G. Benomyl, carboxin, carbendazim, and IBP 48 EC were sprayed 3 times at 14-day intervals,

Sheath blight control with soil fungicides, Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

		1977-78			
Treatment	Dose/ha	Kharif		Rabi	
		Disease incidence (%)	Mean yield (t/ha)	Disease incidence (%)	Mean yield (t/ha)
Thiram + edifenphos	20 kg 0.5 liter	44	3.9	35	2.6
PCNB + edifenphos	20 kg 0.5 liter	54	3.8	36	2.5
IBP17G	35 kg	65	3.7	51	2.5
Benomyl	0.5 kg	62	3.4	47	1.9
Carboxin	0.5 kg	70	3.4	52	2.3
Carbendazim	0.5 kg	59	3.6	40	2.1
IBP 48 EC	1.0 liter	72	3.5	45	2.2
Control		74	3.3	57	1.9
CD (0.05)		8.245	0.406	6.55	0.379